

Tools&Services Working Group

Developments provided by CESSDA

*Slides prepared by Mari Kleemola,
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CESSDA Widening Skopje, November 5-6, 2019

In this presentation

- CESSDA services: CDC and CVS
- Work Plan 2019 tools/services projects: MDO, EQB, Dataverse, PID
- CESSDA Expert Seminar 2019

CESSDA Data Catalogue

- » Version 2.1 in production on CESSDA Technical Infrastructure: <http://datacatalogue.cessda.eu>
 - Over 50 issues addressed in 2 working days. Enhancements tested by User Group before being made live
 - Deleted and rebuilt ES indices for all instances to remove some redundant data
 - Removed UI language options for languages that don't have any associated data
- » Created Issue Tracker for logging and tracking progress against any metadata issues

CESSDA Data Catalogue

- » Now available via EOSC Marketplace:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/cessda-data-catalogue>
- » Preparation for release as Open Source:
 - Added code quality assurance indicators (Jenkins and SonarQube 'badges')
 - Homogenised top-level repository structure wrt non-code files
 - Added copyright & license header to source files
 - Checked for presence of passwords etc
 - Restructured and improved documentation

CESSDA Vocabulary Service

- » Version 1.0 in production on CESSDA Technical Infrastructure: <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu>
- » More DDI CVs to be added in near future
- » Successful implementation of development workflows including user feedback
- » Preparation for release as Open Source:
 - Focus on code quality
 - Added code quality assurance indicators (Jenkins and SonarQube 'badges')
 - Standardised repository top-level file structure

Work Plan 2019 tools/services projects: Metadata Office MDO

- Project leader André Förster (GESIS)
- Task 1 (CMM, metadata requirements, advice and consultation to CESSDA projects, tools and SPs)
 - development of CMM and profiles (agenda item 13.07)
 - meeting and DDI workshop in Cologne mid-October
 - collaboration with training on CMM, CVS and CDC

Work Plan 2019 tools/services projects: Metadata Office MDO

- Project leader Sharon Bolton (UKDA)
- Task 2 (ELSST, controlled vocabularies) European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) is currently available in 13 languages with a 14th, Dutch, to be released in 2019.
- release of ELSST annual update 10 September
- <https://elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk/>
- MDO Basecamp for news and discussion:
<https://3.basecamp.com/3584575/projects/1716357>

Dataverse

- » Dataverse SSHOC Beta version available on CESSDA Technical Infrastructure: <https://dataverse-sshoc-dev.cessda.eu/>
- » European Dataverse Workshop 2020
 - Date: January 23-24, 2020
 - Venue: UiT The Arctic University of Norway
 - <https://site.uit.no/dataverseno/european-dataverse-workshop-2020/>

Work Plan 2019 tools/services projects: Euro Question Bank EQB

- The following EQB slides were prepared by project leader Esra Akdeniz (GESIS)

EQB Application: Result list

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

DE

career

[Reset](#)[Search help](#) Question texts Response categories Study titles Pre- and post-question texts

FILTER & BROWSE

Questions (450)

[Add to basket](#)[Add to comparison](#)

Sort by

Relevance

Collection year

Country

Language

Mode of collection

[Reset all filters](#)

Compare Have you ever used a career guidance service?
 Basket
[Detailed question view](#)
[Response categories](#)
[ZA5914_SU "Eurobarometer 81.3 \(2014\)"](#)

Language

English

Compare To what extent do you agree or disagree...? Q7d Having children restricts the employment and career chances of one or both parents.
 Basket
[Detailed question view](#)
[Response categories](#)
[ZA5900_SU "International Social Survey Programme: Family and Changing Gender Roles IV - ISSP 2012"](#)

Language

English

Compare Which two of the following types of training would you choose in order to further your career and update your skills outside working time?
 Basket
[Detailed question view](#)
[Response categories](#)
[ZA4230_SU "Eurobarometer 62.1 \(Oct-Dec 2004\)"](#)

Language

English

Compare In your opinion, what is the most useful source of information to help improve your study and career prospects?
 Basket
[Detailed question view](#)
[Response categories](#)

Language

Page 1 of 9 50 per page

EQB Application: Study description

Question overview **Study description** Download documentation

Citation: ISSP Research Group (2016): International Social Survey Programme: Family and Changing Gender Roles IV - ISSP 2012. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA5900 Data file Version 4.0.0, [doi:10.4232/1.12661](https://doi.org/10.4232/1.12661)

Study ID: ZA5900

Title: International Social Survey Programme: Family and Changing Gender Roles IV - ISSP 2012

Current Version: 4.0.0, 2016-11-23, [doi:10.4232/1.12661](https://doi.org/10.4232/1.12661)

Date of Collection: 16.08.2011 - 31.01.2015

Series: International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)

Interview Language: English

Methodology:

Geography: Argentina (AR); Australia (AU); Austria (AT); Bulgaria (BG); Canada (CA); Chile (CL); China (CN); Croatia (HR); Denmark (DK); Germany (DE); Finland (FI); France (FR); Great Britain (GB-GBN); Iceland (IS); Ireland (IE); Israel (IL); Japan (JP); Korea, Republic of (KR); Latvia (LV); Mexico (MX); Lithuania (LT); Norway (NO); Philippines (PH); Poland (PL); Russian Federation (RU); Sweden (SE); Switzerland (CH); Slovenia (SI); Slovakia (SK); South Africa (ZA); Spain (ES); Taiwan, Province of China (TW); Czech Republic (CZ); Turkey (TR); United States (US); Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of (VE); India (IN); Hungary (HU); Belgium (BE); Netherlands (NL); Portugal (PT)

CESSDA topics: Family life and marriage, Gender and gender roles

Description: Family and changing gender roles. Topics: attitude towards employment of mothers; role distribution of man and woman in occupation and household; preferred extent of employment for women during different stages of child raising; attitudes towards marriage, cohabitation without marriage, and divorce; attitudes towards single-parenting and childcare by same sex female and male couples (alternative family forms); ideal number of children for a family; attitudes towards

Question overview **Study description** Download documentation

- ▼ Methodology
- ▼ Methodology Fulltext
- ▼ Time Method
- ▼ Mode of Data Collection
- ▼ Sampling Procedure
- ▼ Metadata Provider
- ▲ Publisher

EQB Application: Comparison view

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

EQB 3 English

cessda
Euro Question Bank

vote [View All](#) [Search help](#)

Question texts
 Response categories
 Study titles
 Pre- and post-question texts

[Home](#) > [Search results](#)

The set of questions you have selected in the result list is listed here. You may compare them here side-by-side and switch to other questions you want to compare.

Question no. 1

ZA4800_SU | ZA4800_Q88

Question:
Q75

Question text:
If there was a general election tomorrow, can you tell me if you would vote?

Study ID:
ZA4800_SU

Study title:
European Values Study 2008: Integrated Dataset (EVS 2008)

Study start year:
2008

Study end year:
2010

Study publication year:
2016

Variables

Question no. 2

ZA4800_SU | ZA4800_Q89

Question:
Q75a

Question text:
[Q75: If there was a general election tomorrow, can you tell me if you would vote?]
IF YES: which party would you vote for?

Study ID:
ZA4800_SU

Study title:
European Values Study 2008: Integrated Dataset (EVS 2008)

Study start year:
2008

Study end year:
2010

Study publication year:
2016

Interviewer instruction(s):

Question no. 3

ZA4800_SU | ZA4800_Q92

Question:
Q75b

Question text:
[Q75: If there was a general election tomorrow, can you tell me if you would vote?]
IF NO: Which party appeals to you most?

Study ID:
ZA4800_SU

Study title:
European Values Study 2008: Integrated Dataset (EVS 2008)

Study start year:
2008

Study end year:
2010

Study publication year:
2016

Interviewer instruction(s):

EQB Application: Basket view

The screenshot displays the 'Basket' view of the EQB Application. The page title is 'cessda Euro Question Bank'. The main content area shows a list of 'Selected documents' under the heading 'Questionnaire'. The list includes two items: 'ZA5900_q_de.pdf (Questionnaire)' and 'ZA5900_q_fr.pdf (Questionnaire)'. Below the list, there is a checkbox labeled 'I accept the terms of use' which is checked. A Firefox download dialog box is overlaid on the page, titled 'Öffnen von 2019_04_17_16_28_11_281_5176.zip'. The dialog box contains the following text: 'Sie möchten folgende Datei öffnen:', '2019_04_17_16_28_11_281_5176.zip', 'Vom Typ: Compressed (zipped) Folder (22 Bytes)', and 'Von: http://multiweb.gesis.org'. Below this, it asks 'Wie soll Firefox mit dieser Datei verfahren?' and provides three options: 'Öffnen mit Windows-Explorer (Standard)', 'Datei speichern' (which is selected), and 'Für Dateien dieses Typs immer diese Aktion ausführen'. The dialog box has 'OK' and 'Abbrechen' buttons.

EQB Status report

- Users can browse, discover, compare and download survey questions and question related information
- Prototype is available within the CESSDA infrastructure (internally only) with 3 example studies: <https://euroquestionbank-dev.cessda.eu/>
- Started to do harvesting of OAI-PMH sources from partners
- Next steps: Launch of a stable search service end of 2019; expand coverage to more SP and metadata; integrate EQB into CDC; EQB Workshop in November

Work Plan 2019 tools/services projects: PID

- Project leader Brigitte Hausstein, GESIS
- Deliverables have been sent to the MO:
 - CESSDA ERIC Checklist for the Usage of Persistent Identifiers
 - CESSDA ERIC Persistent Identifier Policy 2019. Principles, Recommendations and Best Practices
 - Report on the Impact of the PID Policy on CESSDA Tools and Services.

CESSDA Expert Seminar 2019

- 26-27 September 2019, hosted by UKDA, Colchester; program coordinated by the T&S WG
- Focussed on data access, tools and services
- 34 attendees from 15 organisations, 20 presentations and very good discussions
- Feedback from participants very positive, overall score 4.65/5
- Most valuable aspects included: discussion sessions, networking, hearing from others' experiences, information on data access conditions, and hearing from (new) tools.

For details, see

<https://3.basecamp.com/3584575/buckets/1716387/messages/2113625070>

CESSDA's Services Timeline

	Tools & Services	Data Users	Data Producers	Service Providers	Funders / Members
2018	CESSDA Data Catalogue				
	ELSST Multilingual Thesaurus				
2019	CESSDA Vocabulary Service				
	CESSDA European Question Bank				
	CESSDA Quality Assurance				
	CESSDA Self-Archiving				
2019	Single Sign On / Easy Access				
	CESSDA Access to Sensitive Data				
2020	Social Sciences Data Exploration Tools				
	Social Sciences Research Data Management				
	CESSDA Data Tags				

Thank you!

T&S WG members:

- *Mari Kleemola - mari.kleemola@tuni.fi*
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- *Anne Sofie Fink Kjeldgaard*
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